

International Conference on **ICGB 2017** Green Banking Perceptions and Challenges

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Banking with Technology—Green Banking

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Abstract—Green banking refers to the adoption of environmental-friendly practices for reducing the carbon footprint from our regular banking activity. Green Banking being a recently conceptualized branch of knowledge, in the year 2009 is yet to take its blossom in the context of banking and economy at global level. This study is based on Secondary data which focused on Research Papers and related articles. Finally we can concluded that in India, the green banking system or the process is not fully activated. Green banking is a concept of taking initiative in a smartest way of thinking for a future growth. Green banking plays a significant role in the global development and response to the global warming. For the protection of our environment government as well as every banks should the initiative in respect of green banking practices.

Keywords: Protection, Technology, RBI, Initiative, Go Green

INTRODUCTION

Green banking is an ethical concept in the world. In the protection of hygienic society global warming is a great issue. In global warming issue there is a high possibility of playing significant role of green banking. Green banking is not only corporate social responsibility activity, it also about to keep the world lovable without any damages. It's about reducing carbon footprint from the banking activities for creating eco-friendly environment. The main objectives of green banking is to make clear utilization of organizational resources in accordance with environment as well as society. Green banking as a concept is a smart way of thinking with the future sustainability for our earth. It examines all the factors that the project is environment friendly or not and whether it has any implications on the future people and planet. Green finance as a branch of green banking provides pivotal contribution to the green industry and green economy. Green banking is an effective tool to conduct online business. It was established in western countries and now it was popularized and practiced in most of the countries in the world.

MEANING

Green banking refers to the adoption of environmental-friendly practices for reducing the carbon footprint from our regular banking activity. Green banking includes two approaches. firstly green banking focuses on internal operations of green transformation of all the banks. It means for reducing carbon footprint from banking activities all the banks should adopt appropriate ways of utilizing renewable energy, automation and other measures and secondly all the banks should adopt eco-friendly responsible financing. It is an ethical bank which has the agenda to conserve the earth environment. And it is controlled by some authority. Finally it is a method of creating eco-friendly environment by using online banking, paying bills through online etc.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the green banking concept.
- To study the concept of Banking with Technology –Green banking.
- To highlight Green banking practices by some of the Indian banks.
- To provide valuable suggestions in this regard

RESEARCH DESIGN

- Secondary Research which focused on Research Papers and related articles.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Banking being a recently conceptualized branch of knowledge, in the year 2009 is yet to take it's blossom in the context of banking and economy at global level.

1. Bihari Suresh Chandra (2010), in his research article analyzed the social responsibility of banking sector. He concluded that the role of banks in controlling the environmental damage is extremely important. As per relatively indirect nature of their environmental and social impacts, banks need to examine the effects of their lending and investment decisions. Incorporating environmental and social criteria into business decision making can reduce the adverse impacts of operating activities. Financial institutions can do a lot to assist efforts for corporate social responsibility and achieve sustainability.
2. Bhardwaj and Malhotra (2013) in their study they mentioned various models of green banking practices adopted by Indian companies to grow. Their research methodology is based on case study method. They founded that the banks which are adopting the green banking practices influence the performance of the organization.
3. Garg Shruti (2015) analysed that green banking is really a good way for people to be more aware about global warming and will contribute a lot to the environment and make this earth a better place to live for future generations. She was mentioned that internet banking, mobile banking, green channel counters, kiosk banking, credit card, debit card, etc were integral part of the Green Banking, She Finally concluded that in India, the concept of green banking is catching up and banks are actively looking for ways to portray themselves as a Green Bank.
4. Mahesh *et al.*, (2016), in their research article they proved that green banking is a new trend in banking sector. They tried to find out the ways to Go Green through 'Green Banking'.

GREEN BANKING TECHNOLOGY

- Mobile Banking
- ATM

- E-Banking
- Credit Card
- Solar Energy
- Save Paper
- Debit Card

MOBILE BANKING

Mobile banking is a powerful strategy. On the one hand it is great to have the accessibility to check out the balance, transfer funds and we can pay our bills from our phones. On the other hand it protects the time and energy of the customer; it also helps in declining the use of energy and also helps to reduce paper works from the banks. This paperless facility has been introduced in most of the banks in India. Mobile banking is a new technology to save the time and interest of the customers. For the purpose of conducting financial transactions for his customers, banks or other financial institutions provide these mobile banking services. These services can be used through mobile devices such as phones and tablets. Financial institutions are providing an app for this mobile banking purpose. Through this way the banks are reducing paper works from the regular banking activity.

ATM

Automated Teller Machine is an electronic machine which is generally operated by a customer to withdraw or deposit cash from the bank. For using ATM services the customer needs to have a card from the bank. It is a magnetically coded plastic card which can be easily read by the machine. ATM provides 24-hour services in 365 days. During any time of day or night a customer can withdraw their cash up to a limit. For withdrawal in banking services ATM provides mobility. As far as ATM is concerned, there is no human error; the customer can withdraw any amount without any error. ATMs are more helpful to travelers because there is no necessity to carry out a larger amount of cash; they can obtain cash anywhere with the help of ATM. And also ATMs are providing privacy in banking activity towards the customer. So that they can withdraw any amount without visiting bank branches and it reduces the paper work from the banks and it leads to safeguard the environment.

E-BANKING

E-banking or electronic banking is a system of electronic payment that helps the customer to make the payment through financial institute websites for conducting the range of financial transactions. Online banking system is perfectly attached to the core banking system examined by the bank. E-banking includes information technology on a banking basis. By the way of the computer-controlled system banking services are delivered. In this system the customer need not to visit the banking premises. It is just like E-business in the banking industry. It is also called as virtual banking. Electronic banking is helpful to check the account balances, payment of electronic bills in transfer of funds between the customer. E-banking is

a result of emerging expectations of bank's customer. Here we can find less number of errors while providing services. The customer can transfer the funds through electronically from one place to another place. It consumes very less time and it is a safe and secure method. Through this also we can create eco-friendly environment.

CREDIT CARD

Credit card is a payment card issued by the financial company to the user or card holder. It allows the customers to the make the payment for purchase of goods and services in any where. It is also helps to borrow funds at the time of sale. It also charges interest that are used for short term financing. Credit card also known as plastic money because the customer need not to carry bank notes or bundle of coins in their wallet. Instead of carrying all these we can carry a single card called credit card. It is also helpful in emerging situations. It is one type of loan facility without visiting banks.

SOLAR ENERGY

Solar energy is a beautiful light and heat from the sun. These are two main forms of solar energy. That is Active solar energy and Passive solar energy. Converting the equipment or an action of solar energy in to a useful form. It is called as active solar energy. For example converting the solar energy into electrical energy as a solar cells that can be used in our home. Passive solar energy means solar energy doesn't need any particular action or equipment. For example by strategically placing windows in a house that allows the sunlight to enter and provide the heat. So solar energy is acts as a eco-friendly sources of energy because it directly comes from the sun without involving the burning of fossil fuels. Solar energy can be used to power homes and global business because the sun is sustainable sources of energy. Solar energy is a permanent solution to the environmental problem being caused by burning fossil fuels for generating the electricity. That releases the harmful green house gases in to environment.

SAVE PAPER

Paper can be save in many ways. By doing this we can save many trees. we can save the paper through recycling bin. We can also save the paper by writing it on the back of that used paper. By carefully pull of sticky tape and fold the used paper for re-using purposes. The bank should purchase recycled paper product in which that has been used by the consumers in a highest post. This includes ATM receipts, news letters, envelopes, annual reports, monthly statements, copy paper etc. Instead of using paper card we can use e-card, purchase online tickets on our phone and we can buy e-books for reader. Through this we can save paper. One ton of paper is produced from the 17 full grown trees. Paper is produced from the trees. In respect to conserve forest we should protect the trees and we should recycle the paper to save cutting of more trees. For social responsibility we should spread awareness about the importance of the paper.

DEBIT CARD

In another word debit card is also known as check card or bank card. while making purchases we can use this plastic card instead of cash. When a user performing a transaction the money comes directly from the users bank account. As this is different from credit card because they do not permit the user to make transaction with a negative balance of his bank account. It is normally have a daily purchase limit means it is not applicable to make large purchase with a debit card. Debit card permit the user to withdraw money from their bank account through ATM with or without pin the purchases can be made. If the card has major payment processors logo, it can be work as credit card. There is no necessity to the card holder to take the risk of showing their pin number. When the debit card work as a credit card money will directly come out of user checking account.

FINDINGS

- State Bank of India (SBI) had launched Green Channel counter facility at their branches in 2010 to change the traditional way of paper based banking (SBI, 2014).
- Canara Bank had set up lounge for high-tech banking facilities like internet banking, pass book printing kiosk, ATM, online trading, Tele-banking and cash/cheque acceptor, solar powered biometric operations.
- ICICI Bank had adopted “Go Green” initiative, which involves activities such as Green Products/ offerings (Instabanking, vehicle finance, Home finance), Green engagement (plantation and distribution of saplings) and Green communication (online bill payment, online fund transfer), Green Partner (BHNS).
- HDFC Bank Ltd is taking up various measures in reducing their carbon footprint in the area of waste management, paper use and energy efficiencies.
- Axis bank Ltd had intaited Independent ATM Deployment model in which ten solar based ATM has been set up in Coimbatore circle. Annual reports are send through mails.
- Punjab National Bank (PNB) is conducting electricity audit of offices as an energy conservation and maintained a separate audit sheet for assessing the impact of green initiative taken by them.

SUGGESTIONS

- Banks must adopt a strategic plan to perform green activities on long term basis as well as short term basis.
- Government should outline a broad guideline of green banking for environmental protection, conservation of biodiversity.
- Reserve Bank of India should shape up a concrete guideline for green banking practices.
- Banks can conserve energy and natural resources by paying bills online, remote deposit, online fund transfers, and online statements. Online banking can create

savings from less paper, less energy, and less expenditure of natural resources from banking activities.

- The main contribution by Banks is in financing the Green Projects i.e. Bankers must be aware of the environmental issues and they must go for financing the projects that do not pollute the environment.
- The initiative to be taken by the Banks in spreading the awareness among the clients about Green banking by organizing seminar and symposium. They can organize awareness campaign in schools and colleges. They can participate in the tree plantation and cleanliness programmes in city areas.
- Consumers should be aware that banks offer green checking account because ultimately it helps their profits and not for purely altruistic reasons. They can profit customers as well because many reward checking accounts will pay a high interest rate to bank customers who meet certain monthly requirements.

CONCLUSION

Finally we can concluded that in India, the green banking system or the process is not fully activated. Green banking is a concept of taking initiative in a smartest way Of thinking for a future growth. Green banking plays a significant role in the global development and response to the global warming. For the protection of our environment government as well as every banks should the initiative in respect of green banking practices. Central bank should guide the commercial banks to check whether they are implementing green banking or not. Some of the commercial banks and the financial institutions are not yet adopted the green banking technology in their banks, Due to the lack of knowledge and it is not popularly used by rural people also. The bank should adopt green banking technology in their banks to create environmental friendly atmosphere.

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